

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effect of perceived quality on purchase intention with mediation of perceived value at RevoU Indonesia

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Abstract

Indonesia education sector is rapidly evolving with the integration of EdTech, driven by increased internet connectivity and digital device access. Despite this growth, the purchase intention rate for paid online learning programs remains low, as many consumers favor free trials over committing to full programs. This study aims to analyze the effect of perceived quality on purchase intention, with perceived value as a mediating factor, for RevoU online educational services in Indonesia. In the Indonesian EdTech market, perceived quality and value are critical considerations influencing consumer intention to invest in paid programs. This study uses a quantitative method by distributing questionnaires to 100 respondents who have participated in the free RevoU mini courses. The data were analyzed using SmartPLS 4. The results indicate that perceived quality has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, suggesting that the higher the perceived quality of the educational services, the greater the likelihood of consumer intention to purchase. Additionally, perceived value also positively and significantly impacts purchase intention, highlighting the importance of providing great value to customers. The findings underscore that both perceived quality and value play essential roles in influencing purchase intention, suggesting that RevoU should emphasize consistent quality and communicate the value of its programs effectively to encourage customer intention and also compete in the Indonesian EdTech market.

Keywords: Perceived Quality; Perceived Value; Purchase Intention; RevoU; EdTech

1. Introduction

Indonesia, a diverse archipelago in Southeast Asia, is experiencing a significant transformation in its educational landscape, particularly in the realm of technology. In recent years, the country has been making strides in integrating educational technology (EdTech) into its learning environments. This shift has been largely catalyzed by the increased availability of internet connectivity and the growing accessibility of digital devices, such as smartphones and tablets, across the country. As a result, there has been a surge in the development and utilization of educational technology platforms.

Indonesia, with a population exceeding 270 million, is one of the largest and most dynamic education markets in the world. Despite its size, the country faces significant challenges in providing quality education uniformly across its diverse regions. The traditional education system is struggling to accommodate the needs of such a large and geographically dispersed population. However, recent advancements in technology have paved the way for innovative solutions, leading to the rise of educational technology company like RevoU.

Educational technology companies in Indonesia have seen remarkable growth in recent years. These companies are capitalizing on the growing internet penetration and the increasing affordability of smartphones. RevoU, like many

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other educational technology companies, offers a wide range of educational products and services. The company's success is deeply intertwined with the evolving educational landscape in Indonesia.

RevoU offers a Mini Course as a free trial for those interested in exploring their programs. This two-week course gives people a taste of the RevoU learning experience without any costs. It covers foundational theory and includes practical simulations, case studies, and tips for starting a career in fields like Digital Marketing, Data Analytics, Product Management, and Software Engineering. This trial is a condensed version of their full programs, allowing people to get experience of their program and to decide if the full course is the right fit before committing financially. The experience includes live sessions with industry experts and hands-on exercises designed to replicate real-world challenges.

The high demand for digital skills and the rise of educational technology platforms face the challenge of low consumer interest in purchasing online paid courses. In the World Bank report titled "Edtech in Indonesia: Ready to Take Off" in 2020, it was revealed that only around 5% of Indonesians are willing to continue learning through paid programs. Indonesian people tends to leave platforms once their free trial period expires [1]. This trend is also supported by the fact that parents are more flexible with online learning if it comes from formal educational institutions such as universities or schools [2]. Initially, potential users may have been deterred by the idea of online learning. Many traditional learners preferred face-to-face interaction and were skeptical about the efficiency of online education.

While EdTech platforms like RevoU provide accessible and flexible learning opportunities, the overall willingness of Indonesian consumers to invest in paid programs remains limited, posing significant barriers for Edtech growth. This low purchase intention underscores the importance of understanding how perceived quality and value influence consumer decisions in the EdTech sector. Addressing these factors is critical for RevoU to succeed in a competitive and evolving market. The key research questions this study seeks to answer are as follows:

- Does Perceived Quality have significant effect on Purchase Intention in RevoU?
- Does Perceived Quality have significant effect on Perceived Value in RevoU?
- Does Perceived Value have significant effect on Purchase Intention in RevoU?
- Does Perceived Quality have significant effect on Purchase Intention with mediation by Perceived Value in RevoU?

1.1. Theoretical Framework

1.1.1. Consumer Behavior

In the field of marketing studies, the concept of consumer behavior plays a crucial role in understanding the reasons related to the decisions consumers make when purchasing a product or service. Consumer behavior is a study that discusses the individual, group of individuals, or organizations in making choices, usage, and how a product, service, idea, and experience can provide satisfaction, needs, or desires [3]. Each individual's purchasing behavior varies, as each person has different buying motives. When making a purchase, individuals are influenced by their own motivations, so understanding consumer behavior is necessary to understand these purchasing motives.

Consumer behavior studies examine how the decision-making process utilizes available resources. These resources can include energy, time, or money. Understanding this process is crucial for comprehending consumer behavior [4].

A comprehensive framework named the Consumer Decision-Making Model is used to understand the stages consumers go through when deciding to purchase a product or service. The model consists of six key stages: need recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decision, purchase, and post-purchase behavior [5].

The process begins with need recognition, where the consumer becomes aware of a gap between their current and desired state, such as realizing the need for a new product. This triggers the second stage, information search, where the consumer seeks out relevant data, either from their memory or from external sources like advertisements, reviews, or recommendations. As the consumer gathers information, they enter the evaluation of alternatives stage, where they compare different products or brands based on various criteria like price, quality, or personal preferences.

Once the alternatives are evaluated, the consumer forms a purchase intention, which leads to the purchase decision. However, factors such as situational constraints or the influence of others can intervene and alter the final choice. If the consumer goes through with the purchase, they move to the next stage, which is purchase, where the transaction is made.

Finally, after making the purchase, the consumer enters the post-purchase behavior stage, where they assess their satisfaction with the product. If the product meets or exceeds expectations, the consumer experiences satisfaction, leading to repeat purchases or positive recommendations. On the other hand, dissatisfaction can result in negative feedback or product returns. The model includes a feedback loop, meaning the consumer's post-purchase experience will influence their future decisions and behavior. Throughout this entire process, various external and internal factors, such as social influences, cultural norms, economic conditions, and psychological factors (like motivation or attitudes), shape consumer behavior.

Figure 1 EBM Consumer Decision-Making Model

1.1.2. Education Technology (Edtech)

The Association for Educational Communications and Technology (AECT) defines educational technology as the study and ethical practice of facilitating learning and improving performance by creating, using, and managing appropriate technological processes and resources. This definition emphasizes that educational technology involves not only the development and use of technological tools but also a systematic and ethical approach to enhancing learning experiences and outcomes. It highlights the importance of integrating various technologies to support and improve teaching and learning, ensuring that these technologies are used effectively and responsibly in educational settings [6].

1.1.3. Perceived Quality

Perceived quality is the perspective perceived by an individual regarding the quality or superiority of the goods or services provided based on expectations. With the consumer's perspective on quality, it adds brand value that can give consumers a reason to choose that brand over others. With the emphasize of its role in shaping consumer perceptions and preferences. He articulated that perceived quality is not solely determined by the actual quality of a product or service but rather by the consumer's perception of that quality [7].

Perceived quality is a crucial component of brand equity and a significant driver of consumer behavior. He emphasizes that perceived quality is the consumer's judgment about the overall excellence or superiority of a product or service compared to alternatives. Kotler emphasizes that perceived quality is essential for differentiation in competitive

markets. High perceived quality can lead to increased customer loyalty, greater willingness to pay premium prices, and positive word-of-mouth referrals [3].

Perceived quality is based on three key principles [8]:

- Quality stems from both product-related and non-product factors that meet consumers' expectations and desires.
- Quality is determined by consumer perception, with perception being more crucial than the actual reality. Even if the product quality is objectively high, it is considered low if consumers perceive it that way.
- Quality is evaluated in comparison to competitors, meaning it is measured relatively. Consumers' perceptions of quality are influenced by competitive dynamics, and understanding how they view a brand allows companies to take actions to enhance that perception.

The concept of perceived quality in relation with SERVQUAL that revolves around how consumers evaluate the quality of a service or product based on their expectations and experiences. According to the the indicators for perceived quality are as follows [9]:

- Tangibles: The facilities, equipment, and appearance of personnel.
- Reliability: The ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately.
- Responsiveness: The willingness to help customers and provide prompt service.
- Assurance: The knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence.
- Empathy: The provision of caring, individualized attention to customers.

In developing and validating measures on understanding how consumers perceive and evaluate brands create indicators. These indicators of perceived quality are as follows [10]:

- High Quality, this indicator emphasizes the comparative aspect of perceived quality, indicating that consumers view the brand as superior in quality compared to its competitors.
- Best in Class, this indicator highlights the brand's position within its category, suggesting that consumers perceive it as the top choice, reflecting a strong association with quality.
- Performance Superiority, this indicator focuses on the reliability and performance aspect of perceived quality, suggesting that consumers believe the brand offers superior performance consistently.
- Consistency in Quality, this indicator stresses reliability and consistency, important facets of perceived quality, reinforcing the idea that the brand delivers high quality consistently over time.

1.1.4. Perceived Value

Perceived value refers to a customer's assessment of a product based on their preferences, expectations, and experiences, involving an evaluation of product attributes, performance, and the outcomes of its use. Essentially, customers determine how well a product helps them achieve personal goals and meet their needs in specific situations. It also distinguishes between desired value [11]:

- what customers hope to achieve received value.
- the actual satisfaction derived from using the product.

This model emphasizes that customer value is not static, it evolves over time as customers gain new experiences and adjust their perceptions and preferences, which ultimately influence their purchasing decisions.

Perceived value is a consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is received and what is given. Holbrook emphasizes that value is highly subjective, varying from person to person and shaped by individual preferences, experiences, and emotions. His definition expands on the idea that value is not just functional or economic, but also multidimensional, encompassing emotional, social, and experiential aspects. His framework identifies several indicators of value [12]:

- Extrinsic value: The functional or practical benefits of the product.
- Intrinsic value: The personal enjoyment or experiential value derived from the product.
- Self-oriented value: How the product benefits the individual consumer.
- Other-oriented value: How the product affects others, or how others perceive the consumer.

- Active value: Direct interaction with or use of the product.
- Reactive value: Appreciation or evaluation of the product without direct interaction.

Customer value is a comparison related to the sacrifices consumers make with the benefits they receive. The sacrifices referred to can be like the costs incurred to obtain the desired product, travel time, and other risks. The difference between what has been obtained and what has been expended is called perceived value [13].

Perceived value is the consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product or service based on the perception of what is received and what is given. This encompasses the trade-off between the benefits received and the costs incurred. She also creates four different definitions of value, these are value is low price, value is whatever I want in a product. value is the quality I get for the price I pay, value is what I get for what I give [14].

In developing and validating measures of facets of customer-based brand equity (CBBE) that focuses on understanding how consumers perceive and evaluate brands. The indicators of perceived value are as follows [10]:

- Monetary Value, this indicator assesses whether consumers believe that the benefits or quality of the product justify its price. It reflects the consumer's judgment about whether the value received (such as performance, quality, or satisfaction) is proportionate to the amount paid.
- Overall Value, this indicator captures the consumer's overall assessment of the product as a worthwhile purchase. It encompasses multiple factors, including the product's price, quality, and the time and effort involved in obtaining it.
- Comparative Value, this indicator measures how consumers perceive the product's value relative to similar products from competing brands. It highlights the comparative aspect of perceived value, suggesting whether consumers believe they are getting more (or less) value from this brand than from others.
- Perceived Value, this indicator assesses the consumer's feeling of satisfaction with the returns received from their investment in the product. It focuses on the subjective experience of value realization after using the product.

1.1.5. Purchase Intention

Consumer purchase intention is the desire within buyers that can influence individual behavior to make a purchase or product selection based on their experiences during product selection, usage, or consumption. Purchase intention is a critical aspect of consumer behavior that reflects the likelihood of a consumer planning to buy a product or service. Purchase intention often serves as a predictor of actual buying behavior, indicating that if consumers express a high intention to purchase, they are more likely to follow through with the transaction. The purchase intention Indicators according to Kotler and Keller are [15]:

- Transactional, which is an individual's desire to make product purchases.
- Referential, which is an individual's desire to provide product references to others.
- Preferential, which is an individual's preference-based behavior towards a particular product. Preferences may change if there is something with the preferred product.
- Exploratory, which is an individual's desire to know about the desired product and gather information to support its positive attributes.

Purchase intention is a consumer behavior influenced by motivation, circumstances that drive an individual to fulfill desires in performing a specific activity to achieve a goal. In making a purchase intention, one requires motivation that drives the behavior to buy. With motivation within an individual, it forms a desire to seek information, recommend to others, purchase, or dispose of the product.

Purchase intention refers to the likelihood that customers will plan or be willing to buy a specific product or service. Purchase intention refers to the cognitive readiness of a consumer to engage in the buying process of a product or service. It is a significant predictor of actual purchasing behavior, influenced by various factors, including consumer attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and emotional responses. He emphasizes the importance of understanding the underlying motivations that drive purchase intentions, such as personal preferences, societal influences, and marketing factors [16].

1.1.6. Effect of Perceived Quality on Purchase Intention

Perceived quality refers to the buyers' perception of the quality of the products and services provided based on consumers' expectations. The products and services offered can shape the perception of quality in the eyes of customers, which can influence consumers' purchase intentions. A good perception of quality regarding a product/service in the minds of buyers is expected to enhance consumer purchase intentions, as it strengthens the reasons for someone to choose that brand, thus forming purchase interest in a particular product or service [17][18]. A direct positive effect was observed of perceived quality on purchase intention [19][20][21], found that perceived quality has a direct positive relationship with purchase intention.

H1: Perceived Quality has significant effect on Purchase Intention

1.1.7. Effect of Perceived Quality on Perceived Value

Perceived quality significantly influences customers' perception of value. By establishing a brand as a reason for purchasing, it differentiates itself from other brands. Perceived value is also rooted in the differences between what customers receive and what they sacrifice across various options. Perceived quality impacts perceived value based on the quality and worth of a product that customers consume. The higher the quality of a product, the greater the value it holds, resulting in customers feeling fulfilled in their desires and needs.

The concepts of perceived quality and perceived value share similarities [22]. However, the uniformity of these concepts is often viewed as equivalent, as perceived value has been demonstrated to be a multidimensional concept of the benefits and sacrifices experienced by customers [23]. On the other hand, perceived quality is defined as the customer's assessment of the overall superiority of a product [14]. Therefore, while quality is one of the main benefits sought by customers, it is not synonymous with value.

The relationship between perceived quality and perceived value, indicating that higher quality perception typically leads to a higher perceived value [24]. Quality, not price, is the primary determinant of perceived value for products and services [25]. Additionally, the higher perceptions of quality can enhance customers' perceived value of a product [26].

H2: Perceived Quality has significant effect on Perceived Value

1.1.8. Effect of Perceived Value on Purchase Intention

The positive effect of perceived value on purchase intention is one of the most significant factors influencing buying intention [14]. Perceived value is based on the overall assessment of the costs and benefits of a specific market offering, reflecting the net benefits received by customers. To maintain a long-term relationship between customers and a brand's products, perceived value cannot solely be the main determinant; it also plays an important role in influencing purchase intention [27]. A high perceived value of a product can influence customers to have purchase intention. This is due to the perceived value associated with the customer satisfaction provided by the company.

H3: Perceived Value has significant effect on Purchase Intention

1.1.9. Effect of Perceived Quality on Purchase Intention mediated by Perceived Value

This research explains the importance of perceived quality and perceived value, which impact the occurrence of purchase intention for a product. Quality and value positively influence customers' perceptions regarding their decision to make a purchase intention [28]. The higher the perceived quality provided, the greater the satisfaction experienced by customers. Likewise, the perceived value of a product or service increases the likelihood of purchase intention by a customer.

H4: Perceived Quality has significant effect on Purchase Intention mediated by Perceived Value

1.2. Hypothesis

Hypothesis is a tentative answer drawn from the relationship between two or more variables as a temporary solution to address the research question. This answer is still temporary or not final and needs further testing. Hypotheses serve as temporary answers to the formulation of research problems, expressed in sentences [29]. Results and discussion. The hypotheses in this study are:

- H1: Perceived Quality has significant effect on Purchase Intention

- H2: Perceived Quality has significant effect on Perceived Value
- H3: Perceived Value has significant effect on Purchase Intention
- H4: Perceived Quality has significant effect on Purchase Intention mediated by Perceived Value

Figure 2 Hypothesis Model

2. Methods

2.1. Research Type

The quantitative approach in this study is the explanatory type. explanatory research as a study aimed at clarifying the relationship between variables to be examined and used to formulate hypotheses [28]. The purpose of this research is to explain the relationship between variables. With explanatory research, the researcher must formulate hypotheses as the first step to explain the relationship between the variables to be studied. These variables consist of independent variable, which is perceived quality (X), mediating variable, which is perceived value (Z), and the dependent variable, which is purchasing intention (Y).

This research is cross-sectional research. The design used is single cross-sectional because each sample from the population is only used once. Cross-sectional research is a study conducted to examine the dynamics of the correlation between risk factors and effects, using a point-in-time approach for observation or data collection [28]. This means that measurement or observation is carried out only once at a specific moment, making this type of research non-continuous or non-longitudinal.

2.2. Population and Sample

1. Population

Population refers to the object or subject of study characterized by the researcher, enabling them to decide whether to study or draw conclusions. This study includes the entire population of consumers who have participated in the RevoU mini course program and reside in Indonesia [28].

2. Sample

A sample represents the size and characteristics of the population. By using a sample, researchers can efficiently manage the use of funds, time, and energy if the population under study is too large. The sample obtained from the population needs to be representative because its conclusions are applied to the population [28]. Since the exact population size is unknown, this study takes a sample of 100. The exact population size cannot be determined because it comprises all consumers who participated in the RevoU mini course program and reside in Indonesia. When determining a sample size for an unclear population, a direct sample of 100 will suffice. In this study, the sample size used is 100 individuals [29].

2.3. Sample Gathering Technique

Through sampling in the study, nonprobability sampling techniques can be used as a method without providing equal opportunity for each population member to be selected as a sample. This study utilizes purposive sampling method,

which is a technique in determining samples based on certain criteria [28]. The study employs purposive sampling, selecting only those who meet the criteria to be research subjects, namely consumers who want to or have participated the RevoU program and reside in Indonesia

The data collection process will involve distributing questionnaires directly or online to consumers who have participated in the RevoU mini course program and reside in Indonesia, and who meet the predetermined criteria.

The characteristics of the selected participants are as follows:

- Have participated in the Mini Course offered by RevoU
- Are at least 17 years old
- Reside permanently or temporarily in Indonesia
- Are willing to fill out the questionnaire related to the conducted research

2.4. Measurement Scale

The measurement scale is an agreement as a guideline for establishing the measurement instrument intervals to produce quantitative data. If using the measurement scale, the variable value can be measured through a specific instrument in the form of numbers with the aim of obtaining accurate, communicative, and efficient results [28].

The Likert scale was chosen as the measurement in this study. Data were obtained through the completion of questionnaires consisting of questions or statements from the respondents, which were then measured using the Likert scale. With the use of the Likert scale, the measured variables are further clarified as variable indicators. These indicators are then used as references to create instruments in the form of questions or statements [28]. Responses to the instruments have levels, ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Each response from the respondents is given a score as follows:

- Strongly agree 5
- Agree 4
- Neutral 3
- Disagree 2
- Strongly disagree 1

2.5. Outer Model Analysis

The outer model, often referred to as the outer relation or measurement model, defines how each indicator block relates to its corresponding latent variable. This model is crucial for assessing the validity and reliability of the measurement constructs within the research. To evaluate the outer model, several tests are conducted. Convergent validity is assessed through the loading factor value on the latent variable with its indicators, where a loading factor value greater than 0.7 is ideal. Discriminant validity is determined by the cross-loading factor, ensuring that the loading value of each construct is greater than its loading with other constructs. Additionally, the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio should be below 0.90, and, in the Fornell-Larcker test, the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) should be greater than the correlations between constructs. For composite reliability, values above 0.7 indicate high reliability, while the expected AVE value for each construct is above 0.5. Lastly, Cronbach's alpha is expected to exceed 0.7 across all constructs to ensure internal consistency. The tests described above apply to the outer model for reflective indicators, while formative indicators require a different approach, focusing on the significance of weights, which must show a significant weight value between the formative indicator and its construct.

2.6. Inner Model Analysis

The purpose of inner model analysis in SmartPLS is to examine the relationships between latent variables, or constructs, within the research model, also known as the structural model. This analysis primarily focuses on testing hypotheses regarding the causal links between constructs, as well as evaluating the strength and significance of these relationships. The first step involves using the R-Square metric to assess the structural estimate of the model. By obtaining an R-Square score, researchers can evaluate the model's goodness-of-fit, with scores interpreted as follows: a strong model at 0.75, a moderate model at 0.50, and a weak model at 0.25. This score can further explain the substantive impact of exogenous latent variables on endogenous variables. The next step, estimating path coefficients, is conducted to determine the significance of relationships between variables by examining parameter coefficient scores and T statistics derived through bootstrapping. Finally, predictive relevance is assessed to determine whether each variable construct contributes meaningfully to the research model's measurement.

2.7. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine the effect or relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The significance level used in this study is 5%. If the selected significance level is 5%, the significance level or confidence level is 0.05 to reject a hypothesis. The following is the basis for decision making:

- H_0 is rejected, if Significance $t < 0.05$
- H_0 is accepted, if Significance $t \geq 0.05$

The indirect influence test applies the bootstrapping method using SmartPLS. This test is carried out to find out how big the indirect influence score is between variables. Satisfaction is considered to be able to mediate the influence of the independent (exogenous) variable and the dependent (endogenous) variable if the statistical T score exceeds the T table score and the P value is below the sig level used at 5%.

3. Results

3.1. Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The purpose of outer model analysis is to evaluate the reliability and validity of the measurement model, which defines the relationships between the observed indicators and their underlying latent variables or constructs. It ensures that the indicators accurately reflect the constructs they are intended to measure. Specifically, the outer model analysis assesses two key aspects:

- validity, which determines if the indicators are truly measuring the intended construct.
- reliability, which checks if the indicators consistently measure the same construct.

Conducting a thorough outer model analysis is essential because it ensures the quality of the measurement model before proceeding to the structural model analysis, where the relationships between constructs are examined. Thus, it helps confirm that the data used for hypothesis testing is both accurate and reliable.

3.1.1. Validity Test

Convergent validity testing is conducted to assess the validity of each relationship between indicators and their corresponding constructs or latent variables. This can be evaluated by examining the loading factor of each item and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each variable. An item is considered valid if the outer loading value exceeds 0.7 and the AVE is greater than 0.5. These are the results of the outer loading test:

Table 1 Outer Loading Result

	PI	PQ	PV
PI1	0.833		
PI2	0.874		
PI3	0.870		
PI4	0.822		
PQ1		0.872	
PQ2		0.823	
PQ3		0.747	
PQ4		0.814	
PQ5		0.797	
PQ6		0.859	
PQ7		0.830	
PQ8		0.830	

PV1			0.837
PV10			0.813
PV11			0.855
PV12			0.775
PV2			0.840
PV3			0.816
PV4			0.767
PV5			0.731
PV6			0.743
PV7			0.718
PV8			0.757
PV9			0.775

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

Based on table 1, it is evident that the overall outer loading results have values greater than 0.7, indicating that they meet the validity criteria for each relationship between the indicators and their respective constructs or latent variables. Therefore, the analysis can proceed. Referring to the data above, the outer loading values consistently meet the validity threshold, confirming the validity of the indicator-construct relationships.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is a measure used to assess the amount of variance captured by a latent construct in relation to the variance due to measurement error. In other words, it indicates how well a construct explains the variance in its associated indicators or items. A higher AVE value, generally above 0.5, suggests that the construct explains more than half of the variance in its indicators, demonstrating good convergent validity.

Table 2 Average Variance Extracted

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
PI	0.722
PQ	0.676
PV	0.619

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

Based on table 2, it can be seen that the value of AVE (Average Variance Extracted) on each variable has met the requirements, which is a value of >0.5 so that it can be concluded that the validity test value through Convergent Validity has been met.

The Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlations is a method used to assess discriminant validity, ensuring that different constructs in a model are sufficiently distinct from each other. In this case, a stricter threshold of 0.9 is applied, meaning that if the HTMT value between two constructs is below 0.9, the constructs are considered to have good discriminant validity.

Table 3 Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Test

	PI	PQ	PV
PI			
PQ	0.760		
PV	0.782	0.825	

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

Based on table 3, the HTMT value between PI and PQ is 0.760, indicating that these two constructs are sufficiently distinct from each other. Similarly, the HTMT value between PI and PV is 0.782, which also supports the conclusion that these constructs have good discriminant validity. Lastly, the HTMT value between PQ and PV is 0.825, which is closer to the 0.9 threshold but still within the acceptable range. The discriminant validity of the constructs is acceptable, meaning there is no significant overlap that would suggest a lack of distinction between the constructs in this model.

3.1.2. Reliability Test

The reliability test aims to determine whether the relevant instrument can be used to collect data. This test is a way to see the level of consistency and reliability of a question item so that the item can be considered reliable or reliable. There are two stages in conducting reliability testing, namely using the Composite Reliability test and Cronbach's alpha. The following are the results of the reliability test shown in table:

Table 4 Reliability Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
PI	0.872	0.877
PQ	0.931	0.934
PV	0.944	0.947

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

Based on table 4, it can be seen that the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha values owned by each variable have met the requirements, which exceeds the value of 0.70. In Cronbach's alpha, the highest value is in the perceived value variable of 0.944 while the lowest value is in the purchase intention variable of 0.872 and likewise in Composite Reliability the highest value is in the perceived value variable of 0.947 while the lowest value is in the purchase decision variable of 0.877. In accordance with the results listed, it can be said that the available question items are stable and have a high consistency so that the three variables are considered reliable or their reliability has been fulfilled.

3.2. Descriptive Analysis of Variables

Descriptive analysis has the function of describing the answers from the questionnaire that has been processed in more depth in the form of a frequency table. Based on the recapitulation and interpretation of the three variables tested, namely Perceived Quality, Perceived Value, and Purchase Intention, it can see the tendency of 100 respondent answers that are in accordance with the criteria of this study for these three variables.

3.2.1. Perceived Quality

Table 5 Recapitulation of Perceived Quality

Indicators	Question Items	Score										Total Score	Mean
		5		4		3		2		1			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
High Quality	PQ1	69	69	26	26	5	5	0	0	0	0	465	4.65
	PQ2	74	74	18	18	7	7	1	1	0	0	466	4.66
Best in Quality	PQ3	55	55	31	31	13	13	1	1	0	0	441	4.41
	PQ4	53	53	34	34	10	10	3	3	0	0	438	4.38
Performance Superiority	PQ5	61	61	27	27	12	12	0	0	0	0	450	4.5
	PQ6	73	73	21	21	6	6	0	0	0	0	468	4.68
Assurance	PQ7	76	76	17	17	7	7	0	0	0	0	470	4.7
	PQ8	73	73	17	17	10	10	0	0	0	0	464	4.64
Mean Score Variable												4.58	

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

- PQ1: Compared to other brands of online learning, RevoU is of very high quality.
- PQ2: RevoU high quality content is evident in the learning materials that they provided.
- PQ3: RevoU is the best brand in its service class.
- PQ4: RevoU stands out as the best in class among competitors.
- PQ5: RevoU consistently performs better than all other brands of online learning.
- PQ6: The performance RevoU instructors is accordance to their qualifications and expertise.
- PQ7: I can always count on RevoU online learning service for consistent high quality.
- PQ8: I am assured of a consistent level of quality in both course delivery and continuous support by RevoU.

In question item “RevoU is the best brand in its service class” (PQ3), 55 respondents (55%) strongly agreed with the statement, while 31 respondents (31%) agreed. A smaller group of 13 respondents (13%) remained neutral, and 1 respondent (1%) disagreed. This indicator scores below the average at 4.41, showing that the respondents feel less strongly about RevoU as the best brand in its service class compared to other competitors. The respondents stated that “RevoU biggest drawback is the lack of an all-in-one website. It relies heavily on third-party websites which requires students to remember multiple links depending on their specific functions” and “RevoU is one of the best, but it cannot yet be considered the absolute best, as there are other bootcamps with offline and more interactive learning systems compared to Revo”.

In question item “RevoU stands out as the best in class among competitors” (PQ4), 53 respondents (53%) said they strongly agreed, and 34 respondents (34%) agreed with the statement. A total of 10 respondents (10%) were neutral, and 3 respondents (3%) disagreed. Similarly, PQ4 falls below the average at 4.38, indicating that while respondents do not really believe RevoU stands out among competitors. The respondent stated that “There are other bootcamps that are not only better but also more affordable compared to RevoU” and “It’s still difficult to say which is the most outstanding. However, so far, when mentioning RevoU to friends or colleagues, the brand remains familiar to them”.

In question item “RevoU consistently performs better than all other brands of online learning” (PQ5), the majority of respondents, 61 respondents (61%), said they strongly agreed, and 27 respondents (27%) agreed with the statement. Meanwhile, 12 respondents (12%) remained neutral. The mean for PQ5 is also below the average at 4.50, suggesting that RevoU performance compared to other brands is not really better than competitors. The respondents stated that “I cannot make a direct comparison because there isn’t an ‘apple to apple’ equivalent available for online digital marketing courses” and “The course is great but the learning pace is really fast so there are some topics that did not explained deeply”.

The mean scores for PQ1, PQ2, PQ6, PQ7, and PQ8 are all higher than the overall average of 4.58, indicating strong perceptions of these aspects of RevoU quality. PQ3, PQ4, and PQ5 are slightly lower, meaning that respondents do not rate these aspects as highly. The average mean score for Perceived Quality is 4.58, indicating that the majority of respondents have a very positive perception of RevoU quality. The highest-scoring indicator is PQ7 (4.70), suggesting that respondents strongly agree that they can rely on RevoU for consistent quality. Meanwhile, the indicator with the lowest mean score, PQ4 (4.38), reflects not so strong agreement that RevoU stands out among competitors.

The assessment of the Perceived Quality variable uses interval measurement levels to make it easier to categorize respondents' perception levels. There are 5 (five) categories of respondents' answers, namely strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. To assess the Perceived Quality variable, interval measurements use the following formula.

$$I = R/K$$

Description:

I: Interval

R: Range (highest interval value minus lowest interval value)

K: Number of classes

The questionnaire related to the Perceived Quality variable includes 8 statement items using a scale of 1 - 5, with answer categories including strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. The following is a calculation of the interval width.

$$I = ((8 \times 5) - (8 \times 1)) / 5$$

$$I = ((40)-(8))/5$$

$$I = 6.4$$

Table 6 Perceived Quality Categorization

No	Score	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	>33.6 – 40	Very Good	77	77
2	>27.2 – 33.6	Good	17	17
3	>20.8 – 27.2	Neutral	6	6
4	>14.4 – 20.8	Not Good	0	0
5	>8 – 14.4	Very Not Good	0	0
Total			100	100

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

Based on the table, it can be concluded that the quality at RevoU Indonesia is very good. This is evidenced from the frequency categorization table as many as 77 percent are in the very good category, so it can be said overall that the Perceive Quality variables in this study are classified as very good.

3.2.2. Perceived Value

Table 7 Recapitulation of Perceived Value

Indicators	Question Items	Score										Total Score	Mean
		5		4		3		2		1			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Extrinsic Value	PV1	44	44	41	41	14	14	1	1	0	0	429	4.29
	PV2	66	66	23	23	10	10	1	1	0	0	455	4.55
Intrinsic Value	PV3	73	73	17	17	9	9	1	1	0	0	463	4.63
	PV4	62	62	27	27	10	10	1	1	0	0	451	4.51
Self-oriented Value	PV5	66	66	23	23	11	11	0	0	0	0	456	4.56
	PV6	65	65	24	24	10	10	1	1	0	0	454	4.54
Other-oriented Value	PV7	62	62	26	26	11	11	1	1	0	0	450	4.5
	PV8	73	73	14	14	12	12	1	1	0	0	460	4.6
Active Value	PV9	70	70	18	18	11	11	1	1	0	0	458	4.58
	PV10	68	68	24	24	7	7	1	1	0	0	460	4.6
Reactive Value	PV11	73	73	18	18	8	8	1	1	0	0	464	4.64
	PV12	68	68	22	22	9	9	1	1	0	0	458	4.58
Mean Score Variable												4.55	

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

- PV1: RevoU courses can help me secure higher-paying jobs.
- PV2: RevoU certificates are recognized by top employers.
- PV3: I find personal satisfaction and fulfillment in learning through RevoU courses.
- PV4: Completing a RevoU course gives me a sense of personal achievement and growth.
- PV5: RevoU programs align with my personal goals.
- PV6: I value the way RevoU courses support my individual learning needs.

- PV7: I value RevoU courses because they make me better equipped to contribute to other people.
- PV8: RevoU helps me to communicate better to other people.
- PV9: Projects in RevoU courses actively help me apply new knowledge to real-world scenarios.
- PV10: RevoU interactive learning format ensures that I actively engage with the material.
- PV11: RevoU student support services respond promptly to my needs.
- PV12: RevoU adapts its courses based on student feedback.

In question item “RevoU courses can help me secure higher-paying jobs” (PV1), 44 respondents (44%) strongly agreed, and 41 respondents (41%) agreed with the statement. However, 14 respondents (14%) were neutral, while 1 respondent (1%) disagreed. PV1 has the lowest score at 4.29 among the PV indicators, falling below the average. Respondents is not really sure that RevoU courses can help secure higher-paying jobs. The respondents stated that “The expectation is that it would be like that, but it has yet to be proven” and “I’m not sure yet, maybe it will be in the future”.

In question item “Completing a RevoU course gives me a sense of personal achievement and growth” (PV4), 62 respondents (62%) strongly agreed, and 27 respondents (27%) agreed with the statement. Meanwhile, 10 respondents (10%) remained neutral, and 1 respondent (1%) disagreed. PV4 is below the average at 4.51, indicating that respondents not sure if completing a RevoU course can be personally rewarding. The respondents stated that “I feel that the course is really hard sometime and I cannot keep up” and “I feel really confused because the materials being taught is new for me”.

In question item “I value the way RevoU courses support my individual learning needs” (PV6), 65 respondents (65%) strongly agreed with the statement, and 24 respondents (24%) agreed. A minority of 10 respondents (10%) were neutral. This score is close to the average but still below at 4.54, indicating that respondents slightly not sure that RevoU can supports their individual learning needs. The respondents stated that “Personally support, but managing them alongside a full-time job makes the schedule feel quite packed” and “There is a support, but RevoU still use outside materials for their program”.

In question item “I value RevoU courses because they make me better equipped to contribute to other people” (PV7), 62 respondents (62%) strongly agreed, and 26 respondents (26%) agreed with the statement. Meanwhile, 11 respondents (11%) expressed neutrality, and 1 respondent (1%) disagreed. PV7 is below the average at 4.50, reflecting a relatively weaker perception of how RevoU can make the respondents better contribute to others. The respondents stated that “Team members sometimes disappear and do not assist with task” and “I experience difficulties in communicating effectively with other team members”.

The mean scores for PV3, PV5, PV8, PV9, PV10, PV11, and PV12 are all higher than the overall average of 4.55, reflecting strong perceived value. PV1, PV4, PV6, and PV7 are lower, suggesting slightly less agreement in terms of these indicators. The average mean score for Perceived Value is 4.55, indicating that most respondents perceive the high value of RevoU. The highest-scoring indicator is PV11 (4.64), highlighting RevoU student support services is very fast in helping the students. The lowest mean score, PV1 (4.29), reflects a disagreement that RevoU courses can help in securing higher-paying jobs.

The assessment of the Perceived Quality variable uses interval measurement levels to make it easier to categorize respondents' perception levels. There are 5 (five) categories of respondents' answers, namely strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. To assess the Perceived Value variable, interval measurements use the following formula.

$$I = R/K$$

Description:

I: Interval

R: Range (highest interval value minus lowest interval value)

K: Number of classes

The questionnaire related to the Perceived Value variable includes 12 statement items using a scale of 1 - 5, with answer categories including strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. The following is a calculation of the interval width.

$$I = ((12 \times 5) - (12 \times 1)) / 5$$

$$I = ((60) - (12)) / 5$$

$$I = 9.6$$

Table 8 Perceived Value Categorization

No	Score	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	>50.4 – 60	Very Good	83	83
2	>40.8 – 50.4	Good	12	12
3	>31.2 – 40.8	Neutral	4	4
4	>21.6 – 31.2	Not Good	1	1
5	>12 – 21.6	Very Not Good	0	0
Total			100	100

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

Based on the table, it can be concluded that the value at RevoU Indonesia is very good. This is evidenced from the frequency categorization table as many as 83 percent are in the very good category, so it can be said overall that the Perceive Value variables in this study are classified as very good. The presence of one response categorized as "Not Good" for perceived value in RevoU evaluation indicates a specific instance where a participant did not find the program to provide the perceived value. This score could come from a mismatch between the respondent expectations and what the respondent gets of the RevoU mini course.

3.2.3. Purchase Intention

Table 9 Recapitulation of Purchase Intention

Indicators	Question Items	Score										Total Score	Mean
		5		4		3		2		1			
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Transactional	PI1	71	71	16	16	13	13	0	0	0	0	459	4.59
Referential	PI2	66	66	25	25	9	9	0	0	0	0	458	4.58
Preferential	PI3	69	69	18	18	13	13	0	0	0	0	457	4.57
Exploratory	PI4	61	61	17	17	16	16	6	6	0	0	434	4.34
Mean Score Variable												452	4.52

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

- PI1: I intend to purchase RevoU full program after I experience the free RevoU mini course.
- PI2: I would recommend RevoU to anyone looking for online learning platform.
- PI3: If I had to choose, I would prefer RevoU programs over other learning platforms.
- PI4: I am interested in exploring what other programs RevoU offers.

In question item "I am interested in exploring what other programs RevoU offers" (PI4), 61 respondents (61%) strongly agreed with the statement, 17 respondents (17%) agreed, 16 respondents (16%) remained neutral, and 6 respondents (6%) disagreed. PI4 is the lowest among the PI indicators at 4.34, falling below the average. Respondents are not that interested in exploring other programs that RevoU offers. The respondents stated that "No, I just want to focus on one field" and "I am not interested in other fields".

The mean scores for PI1, PI2, and PI3 are higher than the overall average of 4.52, suggesting that respondents are strongly inclined to purchase RevoU programs and recommend them. PI4 has the lowest mean score, indicating

relatively weaker intention in exploring additional programs. The average mean score for Purchase Intention is 4.52, which indicates a strong intention among respondents to engage with RevoU offerings. The highest-scoring indicator is PI1 (4.59), showing that many respondents intend to purchase RevoU full program after trying the mini course. The lowest mean score, PI4 (4.34), indicates a weak interest in exploring other programs offered by RevoU.

The assessment of the Purchase Intention variable uses interval measurement levels to make it easier to categorize respondents' perception levels. There are 5 (five) categories of respondents' answers, namely strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. To assess the Purchase Intention variable, interval measurements use the following formula.

$$I = R/K$$

Description:

I: Interval

R: Range (highest interval value minus lowest interval value)

K: Number of classes

The questionnaire related to the Purchase Intention variable includes 12 statement items using a scale of 1 - 5, with answer categories including strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. The following is a calculation of the interval width.

$$I = ((4 \times 5) - (4 \times 1)) / 5$$

$$I = ((20) - (4)) / 5$$

$$I = 3.2$$

Table 10 Purchase Intention Categorization

No	Score	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	>16.8 – 20	Very Good	75	75
2	>13.6 – 16.8	Good	15	15
3	>10.4 – 13.6	Neutral	10	10
4	>7.2 – 10.4	Not Good	0	0
5	>4 – 7.2	Very Not Good	0	0
Total			100	100

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

Based on the table, it can be concluded that the intention of purchase at RevoU Indonesia is very good. This is evidenced from the frequency categorization table as many as 75 percent are in the very good category, so it can be said overall that the Purchase Intention variables in this study are classified as very good.

3.3. Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model)

The evaluation of the structural model, also known as the inner model involves assessing the relationships between latent variables (constructs) in a hypothesized model. It aims to determine the strength, direction, and significance of the paths between these constructs, helping to validate or refute the proposed theoretical framework.

3.3.1. R-Square

The evaluation of the structural model involves assessing the relationships between latent variables (constructs) in a hypothesized model. It aims to determine the strength, direction, and significance of the paths between these constructs, helping to validate or refute the proposed theoretical framework.

Table 11 R-Square Calculation

	R Square
PI	0.558
PV	0.606

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

The R Square (R^2) values in the table indicate the proportion of variance in the dependent variables that is explained by the independent variables in the model. For Purchase Intention (PI), the R^2 value is 0.558, meaning that 55.8% of the variance in Purchase Intention is explained by the independent variables in the model. This suggests that over half of the factors influencing Purchase Intention can be attributed to the predictors included in the model. Similarly, the R^2 for Perceived Value (PV) is 0.606, indicating that 60.6% of the variance in Perceived Value is explained by the model. This reflects a slightly higher explanatory power, suggesting that these variables have a strong influence on Perceived Value. Overall, both values demonstrate that the model has a substantial ability to explain the variability in these key constructs.

3.3.2. F-Squared Effect Size

The f^2 statistic, often referred to as effect size, is used to evaluate the impact or contribution of an independent variable on a dependent variable within a structural equation model (SEM). Specifically, f^2 helps to assess how much an independent variable contributes to explaining the variance in a dependent variable when it is included in the model compared to when it is excluded. In essence, it measures the practical significance of a predictor variable in the model.

The f^2 values are categorized to interpret the effect size:

- Small effect: $f^2 = 0.02$
- Medium effect: $f^2 = 0.15$
- Large effect: $f^2 = 0.35$

Table 12 F-Square Calculation

	PI	PQ	PV
PI			
PQ	0.101		1.539
PV	0.185		

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

Perceived Value (PV), potentially focusing on path coefficients and multicollinearity analysis. The value of 0.101 between Perceived Quality (PQ) and Purchase Intention (PI) suggests a weak relationship, indicating that while Perceived Quality does have an influence on Purchase Intention, its impact is relatively small. On the other hand, the value of 0.185 between Perceived Value (PV) and Purchase Intention (PI) indicates a slightly stronger, though still moderate, relationship. This suggests that Perceived Value plays a more significant role in shaping Purchase Intention compared to Perceived Quality, but it's not a very strong effect.

The 1.539 value associated with Perceived Quality (PQ) and Perceived Value (PV) likely represents the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), which measures multicollinearity between predictors. With a VIF well below the threshold of 5, it indicates that there is no problematic multicollinearity between Perceived Quality and Perceived Value. This means that both variables can be used in the same model without concern for redundancy or overlap in their predictive power. Overall, the table reveals that Perceived Value has a somewhat stronger effect on Purchase Intention than Perceived Quality, and multicollinearity is not an issue in this model.

3.4. Hypothesis Testing

The next step involves testing the hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, and H4) as previously defined. Hypothesis testing is conducted by analyzing the path parameters within the path coefficients and assessing the significance of the T-statistic. This process confirms the correlation between the variables proposed in the hypotheses. The path parameters indicate

whether the hypothesized relationship between variables is positive or negative, and if the p-value is below 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted.

The hypothesis testing was performed using the bootstrapping analysis method, with 5000 subsamples, through the SmartPLS software. The significance of the path coefficients is evaluated by dividing the t-statistic by the t-table value at a 5% significance level, which is 1.96. A path coefficient is considered significant if the t-statistic exceeds the t-table value of 1.96.

Table 13 Hypothesis Data Results

	Path Coefficient	T - Statistics	P - Values	Conclusion
Direct Effect				Accepted
Perceived Quality -> Purchase Intention	0.336	2.449	0.014	
Direct Effect				Accepted
Perceived Quality -> Perceived Value	0.779	14.186	0.000	
Direct Effect				Accepted
Perceived Value -> Purchase Intention	0.455	2.277	0.023	
Indirect Effect				Accepted
Perceived Quality-> Perceived Value -> Purchase Intention	0.156	2.275	0.023	

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2024

The table presents the results summary of the path analysis for the relationships between perceived quality, perceived value, and purchase intention. The first direct effect shows that perceived quality has a significant and positive influence on purchase intention, with a path coefficient of 0.336, a t-value of 2.449, and a p-value of 0.014, making this hypothesis being accepted. The second direct effect demonstrates that perceived quality significant and positive effect on perceived value with path coefficient of 0.779, a t-value of 14.186, and a p-value of 0.000, making the hypothesis accepted. The third direct effect shows that perceived value has significant and positive influences purchase intention, as indicated by a path coefficient of 0.455, a t-value of 2.277, and a p-value of 0.023, making this hypothesis is accepted. Lastly, the indirect effect reveals that perceived quality impacts purchase intention through perceived value, with a significant and positive indirect effect of 0.156, a t-value of 2.275, and a p-value of 0.023, confirming the acceptance of this partially mediating effect.

4. Discussion

In this section, the discussion delves into the results obtained from data analysis using Smart PLS 4 software. The focus is on thoroughly examining the relationships between the variables under study, such as perceived quality, purchase intention, and perceived value. By analyzing the structural model, the discussion aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how each variable influences the others. The findings from this analysis are then interpreted to explain how the variables interact and contribute to the research objectives.

4.1. Effect of Perceived Quality on Purchase Intention

The rise in demand for digital skills, combined with the expansion of educational technology platforms, has been accompanied by a notable reluctance among consumers to purchase paid online courses. The World Bank (2020) report highlights that only 5% of Indonesians are willing to commit to paid learning programs, with many discontinuing after the free trial period [1]. Despite this, perceived quality has emerged as a critical factor in addressing these concerns.

Data from Table 7 reveals that 77% of respondents rated RevoU perceived quality as "Very Good," indicating that a strong perception of quality can overcome hesitation and significantly influence purchase intention.

This finding aligns with the research [31], which demonstrated a positive influence of perceived quality on purchase intention. Similarly, [32][33][34][35] also found that quality, plays a significant role in driving purchase intention. In RevoU case, the quality of content, the company brand compares to other competitor, the performance of instructors and support team, and the consistency of the services contribute to building this intention, encouraging users to move from free trials to paid programs.

The results of the Path Coefficient test confirm a positive and significant relationship between perceived quality and purchase intention. Based on this, H1, which stated, "Perceived Quality has a significant effect on Purchase Intention in RevoU" is accepted. This result suggests that RevoU ability to deliver high-quality educational experiences is key to retaining consumer intention and converting free users into paying customers.

The implications for RevoU from the positive and significant influence suggests that RevoU should continue focusing on maintaining and enhancing the quality of its educational services. Ensuring high standards in course content, instructor expertise, and overall user experience is critical to converting free trial users into paying customers. A consistent delivery of high-quality education could mitigate the hesitation many users feel when committing to paid programs, especially in the highly competitive EdTech market. By emphasizing quality in marketing and user communications, RevoU can strengthen its brand and drive purchase intention in its full programs.

4.2. Effect of Perceived Quality on Perceived Value

In the Indonesian EdTech market, where only a small percentage of users continue with paid programs, perceived value becomes a critical determinant of consumer behavior. The World Bank (2020) report points out that many users leave platforms after free trials due to a perceived lack of value, highlighting the importance of demonstrating worth in online education [1]. In RevoU case, the platform high perceived quality directly influences its perceived value, as demonstrated by the high scores given by respondents in Table 5 and Table 7. The quality of RevoU curriculum, hands-on learning opportunities, and expert instructors enhance the perceived value of the platform.

This result is supported by [31], whose study showed a positive correlation between perceived quality and perceived value. [32][34] also found that perceived value significantly influenced purchase intention. In RevoU case, students who experience high-quality content and teaching are more likely to perceive the programs as valuable and, therefore, justify the financial cost of enrolling in paid courses.

The Path Coefficient test results further confirm the positive and significant influence of perceived quality on perceived value. As a result, H2, which stated, "Perceived Quality has a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value in RevoU" is accepted. This finding demonstrates that RevoU strategy of maintaining high standards of quality not only builds intention but also enhances the perceived value of its programs, making users more likely to invest in the full programs.

The implications for RevoU from the positive and significant influence suggests that improvements in course quality directly elevate the value perception among users. RevoU should prioritize creating a value proposition that highlights both the tangible and intangible benefits of its courses, such as career advancement, personal achievement, and practical skills development. By showcasing these elements in its marketing strategies, RevoU can enhance its appeal to prospective students, encouraging them to perceive the high-quality educational offerings as a valuable investment for their future.

4.3. Effect of Perceived Value on Purchase Intention

One of the key challenges for educational technology platforms in Indonesia is the low conversion rate of free trial users into paying customers. The World Bank (2020) report emphasizes that many users abandon platforms after free trials due to a lack of perceived value [1]. In this context, perceived value is crucial in shaping purchase intention. As evidenced by Table 7, 83% of respondents rated RevoU perceived value as "Very Good," suggesting that users who recognize the value of the platform's offerings are more likely to transition to paid programs.

This finding aligns with the results of [36], who identified a strong positive correlation between perceived value and purchase intention. Similarly, [32][33][34][37] also demonstrated that value plays a key role in driving purchase intention. In RevoU case, respondents emphasized career advancement, self-achievement satisfaction, goals alignment, teamwork building, real-world skills, and services assistance as key contributors to perceived value. These factors directly enhance users' willingness to pay for full programs, overcoming initial hesitation.

The Path Coefficient test confirms the positive and significant influence of perceived value on purchase intention, thereby supporting H3, which stated, "Perceived Value has a significant effect on Purchase Intention in RevoU" This shows the critical role that perceived value plays in converting free users into paying customers, particularly in a market where consumers are initially reluctant to invest in online education.

The implications for RevoU from the positive and significant influence suggests the importance of aligning RevoU programs with the personal and professional goals of its target audience. RevoU should ensure that its services perceived as relevant and beneficial to the user's needs, such as providing career-oriented content, real-world applications, and strong support services. Strengthening the perceived value through testimonials, success stories, and clear demonstrations of program outcomes could further encourage users to transition from free trials to paid programs.

4.4. Effect of Perceived Quality on Purchase Intention mediated by Perceived Value

In the competitive landscape of Indonesia's EdTech sector, the interaction between perceived quality and perceived value plays a crucial role in influencing purchase intention. As highlighted by the World Bank (2020), a significant proportion of users discontinue after free trials due to a perceived lack of quality and value [1]. However, RevoU high perceived quality enhances its perceived value that influence purchase intention. Table 13 illustrates the strong relations between perceived quality, perceived value, and purchase intention, indicating a partial mediating effect.

Previous research [31] found that perceived quality directly enhances perceived value, which subsequently influences purchase intention. This is consistent with the findings of [33][34], that emphasized the mediating role of perceived value in the relationship between perceived quality and purchase behavior. In the case of RevoU, users who recognize the platform's high-quality content are more likely to perceive greater value in the programs, leading to a higher likelihood of enrolling in paid programs.

The Path Coefficient test results confirm the positive and significant of mediating role of perceived value in the relationship between perceived quality and purchase intention. As a result, H4, which stated that "Perceived Quality has a significant effect on Purchase Intention mediated by Perceived Value in RevoU" is accepted. This finding highlights the importance of reinforcing both perceived quality and perceived value to effectively convert free users into paying customers in a market where there is a consumer reluctance toward online education.

The implications for RevoU from the positive and significant influence suggests that both elements must be simultaneously addressed to effectively increase purchase intention in paid programs. RevoU should adopt a holistic approach that emphasizes the high quality of its courses while also reinforcing the value these courses provide. Strategic marketing that connects the dots between quality, value, and desired outcomes such as career progression or skill enhancement can be an effective tool in convincing prospective students of the worth of investing in RevoU full programs.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research, it confirms that the higher the perceived quality of RevoU, the more it positively and significantly increases the purchase intention among potential consumers. Respondents generally indicated strong satisfaction with aspects of quality, such as content excellence, instructor performance, and the consistency of the course. This suggests that when consumers perceive RevoU educational programs as high-quality, they are more inclined to consider purchasing the full paid programs, overcoming initial reservations about online learning.

Based on the research, it confirms that the higher the perceived quality of RevoU, the greater the positive and significant increase in perceived value among users. Respondent's assessment shows that quality attributes, such as comprehensive curriculum, instructor expertise, and reliable support services, contribute to an enhanced sense of value. This perceived value is derived from the alignment of the educational content with consumer expectations and personal goals, which in turn strengthens their overall experience.

Based on the research, it confirms that the higher the perceived value of RevoU, the more it leads to a positive and significant increase in purchase intention. Respondents expressed that when they recognized value in the courses, such as personal advancement opportunities, practical skill development, and relevant certifications. they were more likely to commit to purchasing paid programs. This indicates that perceived value plays a pivotal role in the purchasing decision.

Based on the research, it confirms that the higher the perceived quality of, the greater the positive and significant increase in purchase intention, mediated by partially mediated by perceived value. The findings show that perceived value acts as an intermediary, where high-quality perception leads to enhanced perceived value, which subsequently strengthens purchase intention. Essentially, consumers are more willing to purchase when they perceive that the quality of education justifies the value they receive from it.

5.1. Suggestion

Based on the research results and conclusions, the researcher recommends several strategies for RevoU Indonesia to enhance perceived quality, perceived value, and purchase intention. To improve perceived quality, RevoU could develop an all-in-one platform to centralize student resources, reducing reliance on third-party tools, and explore offline or interactive learning options. Refining unique selling points, competitive pricing, and reinforcing brand identity through clear messaging could position RevoU as a superior choice. Offering flexible course pacing and additional resources for in-depth learning may also enhance its reputation among online platforms. To increase perceived value, RevoU could highlight alumni success stories and provide additional career services, such as resume support and job placement. Adding support to address learning pace challenges, offering self-paced tracks, and creating more in-house content could better align with student needs. For fostering collaboration skills, RevoU could implement structured group activities and add communication skills training. To boost purchase intention, RevoU could emphasize the value of interdisciplinary skills and provide personalized program recommendations to illustrate the benefits of broad-based knowledge. Promoting the long-term value of career adaptability through lifelong learning could further inspire students to explore diverse offerings within RevoU programs, enhancing overall interest and engagement.

For future researchers, while this study used a sample of 100 respondents, a larger and more diverse sample size would offer more comprehensive insights. A larger sample size would enhance the generalization ability of the findings and provide deeper understanding of the different factors influencing purchase intention in the EdTech sector. Future studies could also explore additional mediating variables, such as customer trust, user satisfaction, or brand reputation, to further understand the factors that influence purchase intention in online educational platforms. Expanding the research to include these variables could provide more depth to the current understanding of consumer behavior in the EdTech Industry in Indonesia.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest concerning the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. Furthermore, no competing interests exist between the authors and any institutions, organizations, or products mentioned in the manuscript. This includes products or services that could be considered alternatives to those discussed in the study.

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